

1 Effect of hypercholesterolemia on
2 circulating and cardiomyocyte-derived
3 extracellular vesicles
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5 Csenger Kovácsházi*¹, Szabolcs Hambalkó*¹, Nabil V. Sayour¹, Tamás G. Gergely¹, Gábor B. Brenner¹,
6 Csilla Pelyhe¹, Dóra Kapui¹, Bennet Y. Weber¹, Alexander L. Hültenschmidt¹, Éva Pállinger², Edit I
7 Buzás^{2,3,4}, Ádám Zolcsák⁵, Bálint Kiss^{5,6}, Tamás Bozó⁵, Csilla Csányi⁵, Nikolett Kósa⁵, Miklós
8 Kellermayer^{5,6}, Róbert Farkas⁷, Gellért B Karvaly⁷, Kieran Wynne^{8,9}, David Matallanas⁸, Péter
9 Ferdinandy^{1,10}, Zoltán Giricz^{1,10,†}

10 ¹ Semmelweis University, Department of Pharmacology and Pharmacotherapy, Budapest, Hungary

11 ² Semmelweis University, Institute of Genetics, Cell- and Immunobiology, Budapest, Hungary

12 ³ ELKH-SE Translational Extracellular Vesicle Research Group, Budapest, Hungary

13 ⁴ HCEMM-SU Extracellular Vesicle Research Group, Budapest, Hungary

14 ⁵ Semmelweis University, Department of Biophysics and Radiation Biology, Budapest, Hungary

15 ⁶ HUNREN-SE Biophysical Virology Research Group, Budapest, Hungary

16 ⁷ Semmelweis University, Department of Laboratory Medicine, Laboratory of Mass Spectrometry and
17 Separation Technology, Budapest, Hungary

18 ⁸ University College Dublin, Systems Biology Ireland and School of Medicine

19 ⁹ UCD Conway Institute of Biomolecular and Biomedical Research, University College Dublin, Belfield,
20 Dublin 4, Ireland

21 ¹⁰ Pharmahungary Group, Szeged, Hungary

22 * These authors contributed equally

23 † Corresponding author <giricz.zoltan@semmelweis.hu>

24 Abstract

25 Hypercholesterolemia (HC) induces, propagates and exacerbates cardiovascular diseases via various
26 mechanisms that are yet not properly understood. Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are involved in the
27 pathomechanism of these diseases. To understand how circulating or cardiac-derived EVs could affect
28 myocardial functions, we analyzed the metabolomic profile of circulating EVs, and we performed an in-
29 depth analysis of cardiomyocyte (CM)-derived EVs in HC. Circulating EVs were isolated with Vezics
30 technology from male Wistar rats fed with high-cholesterol or control chow. AC16 human CMs were treated
31 with Remembrane HC supplement and EVs were isolated from cell culture supernatant. The biophysical
32 properties and the protein composition of CM EVs were analyzed. THP1-ASC-GFP cells were treated with
33 CM EVs, and monocyte activation was measured. HC diet reduced the amount of certain
34 phosphatidylcholines in circulating EVs, independently of their plasma level. HC treatment significantly
35 increased EV secretion of CMs and greatly modified CM EV proteome, enriching several proteins involved
36 in tissue remodeling. Regardless of the treatment, CM EVs did not induce the activation of THP1
37 monocytes. In conclusion, HC strongly affects the metabolome of circulating EVs and dysregulates CM
38 EVs, which might contribute to HC-induced cardiac derangements.

39 **Keywords:** exosome, obesity, dyslipidemia, proteomics, metabolomics, inflammation

40 Introduction

41 Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are one of the primary causes of death worldwide¹. Metabolic diseases,
42 including hypercholesterolemia (HC), can induce, propagate and exacerbate CVDs via various mechanisms
43 that are yet not properly understood. Extracellular vesicles (EV) are cell-secreted nano-sized membrane
44 particles with various molecular cargo, including metabolites, proteins and nucleic acids². EVs are involved
45 in the pathomechanism of both CVDs and HC^{3,4}. We have shown earlier that metabolic co-morbidities can
46 ameliorate the innate stress response of the heart^{5,6}, which is mediated by EVs⁷. Furthermore, one of the
47 most common metabolic co-morbidities, type-II diabetes, can inhibit EV-mediated cardioprotection⁸.
48 Besides, EVs of high-fat-fed animals can also exacerbate ischemic cardiac damage and induce cell death of
49 cardiomyocytes (CM)^{9,10}. These results suggest that EVs play a role in CVDs and HC.

50 EVs can regulate target cells via paracrine communication within a tissue or by getting into the circulation
51 they can alter remote tissues. Therefore, to understand how HC play a role in CVDs via EVs, the analysis
52 of both circulating and cardiac EVs is necessary. As of now, it is evidenced that the number of circulating
53 EVs is increased in metabolic diseases¹¹⁻¹³, including familiar hypercholesterolemia^{14,15}, where their amount
54 is associated with the risk of CVDs^{16,17}. However, to understand the biological role of EV-related changes
55 in HC, it is necessary to characterize the composition and content of EVs. The main constituents of EVs are
56 membrane lipids, intravesicular and transmembrane proteins, nucleic acids and other metabolites. Changes
57 in any of these constituents may result in altered biological responses. Barrachina et. al. have analyzed the
58 dysregulated protein composition of circulating EVs in obesity¹⁸, and a similar study also analyzed the
59 miRNA cargo of EVs from obese patients¹⁹. However, how HC affects the metabolic profile of circulating
60 EVs has not been assessed so far.

61 On the other hand, little is known about how HC affects the local EV communication of the heart. An earlier
62 study presented that pathological secretion of endothelial-derived EVs in HC impairs cardiac angiogenesis²⁰.
63 CMs are the main constituent and the functional element of the myocardium. Their EV-mediated regulation
64 of the cardiac milieu might have great importance in CVDs. However, the effect of HC on EVs released by
65 CMs still needs to be addressed. Therefore, to understand the connection between CMDs and HC, an in-
66 depth analysis of CM EVs is necessary.

67 One of the mechanisms that may connect CVDs and CMs and be regulated by EVs is inflammation. Earlier
68 studies showed that CM EVs activate monocytes in various disease conditions, such as in angiotensin II-
69 induced hypertrophy, thereby contributing to inflammation^{21,22}. In contrast, in hypoxic conditions, EVs
70 promote macrophage polarization to the reparative M2 phenotype^{23,24}. These results suggest that CM EVs
71 might play a role in HC-induced inflammation.

72 To fill the gaps and to extend our knowledge on the effect of HC on both systemic and cardiac EVs, we
73 aimed to identify the metabolic alterations in circulating EVs and to analyze CM EVs in HC. Therefore, we
74 isolated rat circulating EVs and compared their metabolomic changes to their plasma metabolome. In
75 addition, for the first time, we assessed how HC affects the biophysical and biochemical properties of CM
76 EVs and we analyzed their role in the activation of monocytes.

77 Results

78 Hypercholesterolemia alters metabolite composition of blood plasma-derived EVs

79 To extend our knowledge of how HC affects circulating EVs, we investigated how HC diet modifies the
80 metabolite composition of circulating EVs and those of plasma (Figure 1. A). We have isolated EVs from
81 rat blood using our protocol validated previously²⁵, which results in non-detectable amount of common
82 contaminants, such as Apolipoprotein A1. Of the 630 metabolites analyzed, 433 were detected in the plasma
83 and only 29 in EVs (see Online Supplementary Material). The total amount of cholesterol esters identified
84 was significantly elevated in the HC group (Figure 1 C) even though HC diet did not increase the body
85 weight of the animals (Figure 1 B). In addition, plasma concentrations of several triacylglycerols (TG) were
86 increased, whereas concentrations of several glycerophospholipids (GP) were decreased by HC diet (Figure
87 1 D, left panel). These results show that our model represents non-obese patients with hypercholesterolemia.

88 HC diet also altered the metabolite composition of EVs. The amount of several phosphatidylcholines (PCs)
89 was reduced in EVs (Figure 1 D, right panel), whereas some showed opposite changes in plasma. Similarly,
90 tendencies for inverse changes in TG levels between EV and plasma were observed (Figure 1 E). To further
91 analyze the connection between plasma and plasma-derived EV metabolites, we correlated intensities of
92 metabolites detected in both plasma and in EVs from the same animal. We found that only the amount of
93 GPs was correlated between plasma and EVs, whereas there was no correlation between plasma and EVs in
94 the concentration of amino acids, amino acid-related metabolites, fatty acids and TGs (Figure 1 F,
95 Supplementary Figure S2). This analysis evidence that HC diet modulates metabolites in EVs and plasma
96 differentially.

97
 98 **Figure 1: Metabolomic analysis of circulating EVs in HC-fed rats.** ($n_{ctrl} = 11$, $n_{hc} = 7$ for all experiments) **A:** Schematic
 99 representation of the experimental plans. Male Wistar rats were kept on normal or HC diet for 12 weeks, then blood was collected
 100 and EVs were isolated from platelet-free plasma. Plasma and EV metabolome were analyzed. **B:** Body weight of the animals. Diet
 101 did not affect body weight. **C:** HC diet increased the amount of cholesterol esters in the blood. **D:** Volcano plot of metabolome
 102 analysis on plasma (left) and EVs (right). In plasma, the intensity of numerous triacylglycerols was significantly reduced, meanwhile
 103 glycerophospholipids and cholesterol esters were enriched by HC. In EVs, the intensity of most glycerophospholipids detected was
 104 decreased by HC. **E:** Heatmap for the metabolites detected both in EVs and in plasma. Multiple metabolites show opposite changes
 105 between EVs and plasma. **F:** Linear correlation of multiple metabolites in EVs vs. plasma. Of the five metabolite groups analyzed,
 106 only glycerophospholipids showed a moderate correlation between plasma and EV intensities (see regression line, $R^2 = 0.502$, $p <$
 107 0.001). * $p < 0.05$ Student's *t*-test CTRL vs HC; For metabolomics analysis (panel E) Benjamini-Hochberg false discovery *p*-
 108 adjustment was applied.

109 HC increases EV release of AC16 CMs

110 To investigate the local effect of HC on cardiac EV, we next analyzed whether HC alters EV production of
 111 CMs using AC16 cells (Figure 2 A). Using Oil-red-o staining, we confirmed that the lipid content of CMs
 112 was increased due to treatment (Figure 2 B). When we analyzed the EV isolates, we found that HC treatment

113 significantly elevated their particle (Figure 2 C and D) and protein concentration (Figure 2 E), suggesting
114 that HC increased EV secretion of CMs. Besides, the size distribution of the isolates remained unchanged,
115 according to NTA measurements (Figure 2 C, Supplementary Figure S3 A).

116 Our EV isolates were positive for EV markers Tumor susceptibility gene 101 (Tsg101) and ALG-2-
117 interacting protein X (Alix), as well as transmembrane EV protein CD81. In addition, EV isolates contained
118 glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) and heat shock protein 70 (Hsp70), which are
119 common cargo proteins of EVs (Figure 2 F and Supplementary Figure S4). We tested potential
120 contaminants, such as ATP synthase lipid-binding protein, Sodium Potassium ATPase and Histone H3, and
121 we found that the samples contained Histone H3. (Figure 2 F and Supplementary Figure S4). We found
122 significant differences in the particle/protein ratio (Supplementary Figure S3 B). These results confirm the
123 EV origin of our membrane particles and that they might contain a certain level of non-EV material.

124 HC treatment did not affect phosphatidylcholine content and elastic modulus of AC16 EVs

125 As we found that HC treatment modified the lipid composition of circulating EVs by decreasing the amount
126 of certain PCs, we analyzed the total lipid and PC amount in AC16 EVs to unravel, whether similar changes
127 can be observed in CM-derived EVs as well. We found that HC treatment did not change the lipid/protein
128 ratio of the samples (Supplementary Figure S3 C). PC content, as normalized to the total lipid content, was
129 also unaffected (Supplementary Figure S3 D). To further analyze the membrane properties of CM EVs, we
130 applied AFM measurements, as cholesterol affects the rigidity, banding and elasticity of plasma
131 membranes²⁶⁻²⁸.

132 Surface mapping revealed roughly circular particles with a partially flattened, curved surface that aligned
133 well with the literature²⁹⁻³². In addition, some associated vesicles and other smaller, rounded or
134 multisegmented objects with a height lower than 10 nm were found, likely lipid- or protein aggregates or
135 vesicle fragments (Figure 2 H). Based on AFM measurements, vesicles detected ranged from 10 to 300 nm
136 in diameter with a median size of around 50 nm with a statistically significant difference between VEH vs
137 CTRL or HC groups (Supplementary Figure S3 E), and vesicle height ranged from 10 to 100 nm with a
138 statistically significant difference between HC vs CTRL or VEH groups (Supplementary Figure S3 F),
139 however, the biological significance of these changes might be minor. Force spectroscopy was used to
140 measure the elasticity of EVs. Elastic moduli were distributed between 10^5 - 10^7 Pa, which was in line with
141 earlier data measured on liposomes and EVs³²⁻³⁴. HC treatment did not affect the elasticity of AC16 EVs
142 (Figure 2 G). These results suggest that, in contrast to circulating EVs, HC does not affect the lipid
143 composition of CM-derived EVs.

144

145 *Figure 2: Analysis of EVs secreted by AC16 CMs. A: Schematic representation of the experimental plans. AC16 human CMs were*
 146 *seeded for 24 hours, and then the medium was replaced with serum-free medium with or without vehicle or HC supplement for*
 147 *another 48 hours, then EVs were isolated from the cell culture supernatant. B: Representative images of oil-red-o measurements*
 148 *on AC16 cells. Blue: DAPI (nuclei), red: Oil-red-O (lipid). Results show increased amounts of lipids upon HC treatment. C: Size*
 149 *distribution of isolated EVs measured by NTA. Vesicles with diameters of 50-300 nm were detected in every experimental group.*
 150 *($n_{ctrl} = 15$, $n_{veh} = 17$, $n_{hc} = 10$) D: Particle number of EV isolates measured by NTA. HC increased the particle number significantly.*
 151 *($n_{ctrl} = 15$, $n_{veh} = 17$, $n_{hc} = 10$) E: Absolute protein concentration of the isolates measured with 280nm light absorbance. HC*
 152 *increased the protein concentration significantly. ($n_{ctrl} = 19$, $n_{veh} = 20$, $n_{hc} = 14$) F: Analysis of EV markers and potential*
 153 *contaminants using Western blot. Whole blots are presented in Supplementary Figure S3. G: Elastic modulus of the isolates*
 154 *measured by AFM. No significant difference was observed. ($n_{ctrl} = 58$, $n_{veh} = 49$, $n_{hc} = 54$, out of at least three independent*
 155 *experiments) H: Representative images of non-contact mode AFM measurements. First row: height-contrast, second row:*
 156 *amplitude-contrast images in the same view field. Arrows: EVs, Circles: Non-EV-like structures, with height < 10 nm. * $p < 0.05$*
 157 *HC vs CTRL and VEH in ANOVA with Tukey's post-hoc test.*

158 AC16 EVs do not activate THP1 monocytes

159 As EVs play a role in inflammation and CM EVs modify immune cells in various diseased conditions^{21–24},
 160 we aimed to investigate the potential inflammatory effects of CM EVs in HC. We treated ASC-GFP-
 161 expressing THP1 monocytes with EVs derived from AC16 CMs in different doses. After 16 hours of
 162 treatment, GFP expression in the monocytes was analyzed by flow cytometry to measure ASC-dependent
 163 inflammasome activation (Figure 3 A). We found that neither control nor HC EVs increased GFP expression
 164 in THP1-ASC-GFP cells (Figure 3 B, Supplementary Figure S5). We further analyzed the gene expression
 165 of pro-inflammatory factors Interleukin 1 beta (IL-1 β), Tumor Necrosis Factor alpha (TNF- α) and anti-

166 inflammatory factor Interleukin 10 (IL-10) in THP-1 cells, after treatment. No differential expression was
 167 observed in any of these genes (Figure 3 C). These results suggest that CM EVs do not activate monocytes.

168
 169 *Figure 3: Analysis of immune cell activation of AC16 EVs using THP1-ASC-GFP. A: Schematic representation of the experimental*
 170 *setup. EVs were isolated from AC16 cells and THP1-ASC-GFP cells were treated with the isolates, then flow cytometry*
 171 *measurement was applied to measure GFP expression and protein expression was analyzed with qPCR. B: GFP expression*
 172 *measured by flow cytometry. LPS significantly increased the percentage of activated cells. EV treatment did not affect GFP*
 173 *expression, regardless of the dose or the experimental group (n = 6, all groups). C: Gene expression analysis of IL-1β, TNF-α and*
 174 *IL-10 normalized to HPRT. No differences were observed (n = 2-3) * p < 0.05 vs PBS; ANOVA with Tukey's post-hoc test.*

175 HC treatment modifies the protein composition of AC16 EVs

176 The previous results refuted our original hypothesis that HC affects the inflammatory effect of CM EVs. In
 177 light of these results, we decided to analyze the protein composition of CM EVs isolated from HC-treated
 178 AC16 cells with liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry, to characterize the effect
 179 HC plays in the regulation of CM EV function. The data were quantified using label-free quantitation (LFQ).
 180 A total of 2235 proteins derived from 2218 genes were identified (see Online Supplementary Material). To
 181 perform a first quality control on our dataset, we compared these genes with the Vesiclepedia^{35,36} database.
 182 A total of 2088 genes overlapped with the database, of which 84 were among the 100 most frequently
 183 identified proteins in EVs (Figure 4 A). These observations reassured us of the quality of our isolation and
 184 the validity of MS-based proteomics to study EVs in our system.

185 To continue our analysis, we next compared the protein composition of EVs between the treatment groups
 186 using standard statistical analysis for proteomics datasets³⁷. Thus, we performed ANOVA tests followed by
 187 Tukey's post-hoc tests. We identified statistically significant differences in the amount of 117 proteins
 188 (Supplementary Table S4), of which, 12 showed differences between the CTRL and VEH groups. Five of
 189 these 12 proteins had significantly different abundance between the CTRL and HC, but not between the

190 VEH and HC groups. Additionally, two proteins had significantly different abundance between the CTRL
191 and HC but not between the VEH and HC groups. Finally, we found 110 proteins with significantly different
192 abundance between the VEH and HC groups (Figure 4 B), which were selected for further analysis to
193 explore proteomic changes induced by HC treatment in CM-derived EVs.

194 When we compared VEH and HC groups, we found that the abundance of 33 proteins decreased, while 77
195 proteins showed increased concentration in EVs upon HC treatment (Figure 4 C). Functional analysis of
196 these proteins using gene ontology among the 33 proteins with significantly smaller amount, we identified
197 numerous extracellular matrix (ECM) (GO: 0031012, FDR < 0.001) or cell adhesion-associated (GO:
198 0005925, FDR < 0.001) proteins. Remarkably, the amount of certain endosomal sorting complexes required
199 for transport (ESCRT) constituents³⁸ was reduced as well (Figure 4 D). Interestingly, most of the proteins
200 with enriched concentration were associated with RNA binding (GO:0003723, FDR < 0.001) of which many
201 proteins are part of the spliceosome complex or ribosomal complex. (Figure 4 D).

202 Altogether, our data show that HC treatment substantially affects the proteomic composition of CM EVs.
203 Enrichment in RNA-associated proteins suggests that the RNA cargo of EVs can be modified as well.
204 However, no specific cellular signalization pathway was identified that would be directly connected to HC-
205 induced cardiomyopathy.

206

207 *Figure 4: Proteomic analysis of AC16 EVs. ($n_{ctrl} = 10$, $n_{veh} = 10$, $n_{hc} = 4$, in all experiments) A: Comparison of the proteins detected*
 208 *with the Vesiclepedia database. A total of 2137 proteins were identified of which 2088 were described in the database and 84*
 209 *proteins were found among the 100 most frequently described EV proteins. B: Venn diagram for the representation of the*
 210 *statistically significant differences between the experimental groups, using ANOVA followed by Turkey's post-hoc test. C: Volcano*
 211 *plot shows significant differences between the VEH and HC groups. D: Interaction network of proteins with significantly different*
 212 *abundance between the VEH and HC groups. LEFT: Proteins with decreased abundance, RIGHT: Proteins with increased*
 213 *abundance.*

214

215 Discussion

216 In the present study, we aimed to get a deeper insight into the impact of HC on circulating and CM EVs.
217 We showed that HC diet reduced the amount of certain PCs in EVs and that changes in the lipid composition
218 of the blood and EVs showed strikingly different patterns. Furthermore, we showed that HC treatment
219 altered both the quantity and protein composition of EVs from CMs. Thus, contrary to our initial hypothesis,
220 we show that HC does not affect THP-1 monocyte activation.

221 Previous works have characterized the proteomics and miRNA-omics of circulating EVs in obesity^{18,19}.
222 Besides, EV-transferred metabolites can affect remote tissues³⁹, we therefore analyzed the metabolic profile
223 of EVs isolated from HC-fed rats. In our isolates, we found that HC diet significantly reduced the amount
224 of multiple PCs in circulating EVs. These results are in agreement with the studies by Blandin *et al.* who
225 evidenced that total PC content was reduced in EVs isolated from adipocytes of high-fat diet fed mice⁴⁰.
226 Our results, together with miRNA-omics analysis of EVs from patients with metabolic disorders¹⁹, suggest
227 that circulating EVs in HC are associated with a stress signal, as the amount of PC in EVs is associated with
228 multiple disease states⁴¹⁻⁴³. However, such changes could be originated from contaminants of the EV isolate,
229 primarily from high-density lipoproteins, the fact that we have applied a well-established protocol that
230 results in an EV isolate in which the markers of common contaminants, such as Apolipoprotein A1 are
231 below the detection limit of western blot²⁵, and that we identified an opposite directional change in
232 lipoprotein-rich plasma, supports that the PC amount of the EV membrane or EV-associated, extravesicular
233 constituents was decreased and such change is regulated independently of that of the plasma. However, for
234 better validation, a more sensitive analysis of possible non-vesicular proteins, such as mass spectrometry
235 could be implemented. As little is known about how the reduction of PCs affects EV-regulated mechanisms,
236 functional experiments and comprehensive analysis of circulating EVs in HC, including how such EVs
237 affect a healthy organism also need to be implemented. In conclusion, metabolic analysis of EVs may
238 provide pathophysiological or diagnostic information on cardiometabolic derangements that might remain
239 shrouded if plasma analysis was performed alone.

240 Importantly, our results, also shed light on how EV-mediated cardiac derangements can be derived from
241 both circulating and cardiac tissue-derived EVs. We analyzed, how HC modulates CM EV secretion. As
242 cardiac stress, such as altered Ca²⁺ concentration or hypoxia, is associated with elevated secretion of CM
243 EVs⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶, our findings that CM EV secretion increases in HC may reflect the stress induced by the altered
244 metabolic environment, similarly to circulating EVs. This is in line with previous observations as such stress
245 response is suggested by Strauss *et al.*⁴⁷, who found that treatment of Oli-Neu cells with cholesterol
246 increased their EV secretion. This mechanism is proposed to eliminate cholesterol from the cells
247 accumulated in the endosomal/lysosomal system in diseased conditions, such as in Niemann-Pick type C

248 lipid storage disease. In addition, the increase in the number of EVs secreted may be the consequence of the
249 higher amount of lipid rafts in CMs, as cholesterol plays a significant role in lipid raft formation⁴⁸ and EV
250 secretion correlates with the amount of lipid rafts⁴⁹. Thus, our results together with previous findings show
251 that cholesterol affects EV secretion through multiple mechanisms.

252 Importantly, we also show that modified EV secretory pathways may alter EV-associated protein
253 composition as well. Our finding that the amount of certain ESCRT proteins decreased in HC EVs supports
254 that HC-induced EV release in CMs may result from elevated cholesterol levels and increased lipid raft
255 formation instead of an enhanced ESCRT-dependent EV secretory pathway. In addition, HC might affect
256 the function of CM EVs in the maintenance of myocardial homeostasis, since the presence of multiple ECM
257 and cell adhesion proteins was reduced in HC EVs or in their protein corona⁵⁰. Furthermore, multiple
258 proteins with tissue-remodeling functions were enriched in HC-treated AC16-EVs. Some of these are
259 Connective tissue growth factor, also known as Cellular communication network factor 2 (CTGF/CCN2),
260 which mediates fibrosis in cardiomyocytes and regulates proliferation, cell adhesion and angiogenesis⁵¹ or
261 Heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein A1 (HNRNPA1), protein CYR61 and DNA (cytosine-5)-
262 methyltransferase 1 (DNMT1) those can be found in cancer cell-derived EVs as well in which they play a
263 role in EV-induced angiogenesis, proliferation, invasion or in vivo metastasis formation of recipient cells⁵²⁻
264 ⁵⁴. Besides, vesicular CYR61 is able to induce the expression of MMP-1 in remote cells as well⁵⁵. In
265 conclusion, these changes in the CM EV proteome may play a role in HC-induced cardiac remodeling.

266 Altered CM EV proteome also represents the physiological and metabolic status of their donor cells. Li *et*
267 *al.* showed that the elevated amount of CYR61 in circulating EVs is associated with acute coronary
268 syndrome⁵⁶. Besides, the level of Gap junction alpha-1 protein, also known as Connexin-43 (GJA1, CX43)
269 is decreased in circulating and CM EVs after myocardial infarction⁵⁷. As the same changes in CYR61 and
270 GJA1 were identified in HC-treated AC16 EVs, it may represent the stressed conditions of the donor cells.
271 In addition, multiple proteins enriched in CM EVs after HC treatment, such as DNMT1, HNRNPA1,
272 Double-stranded RNA-binding protein Staufen homolog 1 (STAU1) and Gamma-interferon-inducible
273 protein 16 (IFI16) regulate the expression of various genes involved in lipid metabolism and adipocyte
274 differentiation⁵⁸⁻⁶¹. As CM EVs reach the circulation⁶² and establish communication between cardiac and
275 adipose tissue⁶³⁻⁶⁵, these changes might aim to alleviate dyslipidemia and indicate the stressed metabolic
276 condition of the CMs.

277 As most of the proteins that had elevated amounts in EVs after HC treatment bind RNA and some of these,
278 such as GJA1, Nuclease-sensitive element-binding protein 1 (YBX1), Heterogeneous nuclear
279 ribonucleoproteins A2/B1 (HNRNPA2B1) and HNRNPA1 play active role in RNA packaging to EVs⁶⁶⁻⁷¹,
280 we suggest that the RNA content of EVs is changed in HC as well, similarly to circulating EVs in obesity¹⁹.

281 Also, complete 40S ribosomal subunits are presumably released in HC EVs, as the amount of most of its
282 proteins was increased. However, the relevance of these changes needs further elucidation. In conclusion,
283 our results indicate that HC treatment has a diverse effect on the molecular composition of CM EVs. Similar
284 to circulating EVs, these changes outline a stress signal of the CMs propagated by EVs. To validate the
285 suggested functional effects and to unravel whether these changes contribute to or compensate for HC-
286 induced cardiac abnormalities, further functional experiments will need to be performed.

287 As EVs contribute to the physiological function of the immune system⁷², and since HC induces inflammation
288 in multiple organs, including the heart and CM EV secretion is increased in inflammation⁶², it seemed
289 plausible that EVs released from CMs in a HC environment may contribute to the activation of immune
290 cells. However, our findings indicate that EVs derived from HC-treated CMs do not induce inflammasome-
291 mediated activation of monocytes. This is also suggested by our proteomic analyses, which revealed a
292 reduced abundance of the immunogenic protein HLA class I histocompatibility antigen, B-7 alpha chain
293 (HLA-B). Of note, these findings are in contrast with earlier studies on circulating EVs from obese patients
294 where an increased amount of various immunoglobulins and Complement C4-B protein was observed¹⁸,
295 suggesting a pro-inflammatory phenotype. This contradiction indicates that CM- and circulating EVs might
296 have opposing effects in the context of inflammation in HC. According to our results, as opposed to our
297 original hypothesis, we concluded that CM EVs do not contribute to monocyte activation via inflammasome
298 activation. However, further experiments may provide additional insights into the role of CM EVs in
299 inflammation.

300 As we found that the amount of certain PCs was decreased in circulating EVs, we have analyzed the total
301 PC content of CM EVs. Interestingly, the PC concentration in CM EVs was unchanged. Besides, the lipid
302 to protein ratio and the membrane rigidity, defined by the membrane composition, remained unchanged in
303 CM EVs as well. However, a complete comparison of the two EV sources, including both metabolomics on
304 CM EVs and proteomics on circulating EVs may result in correlations between the sources, our results
305 suggest that CM EVs are regulated differently in HC than circulating EVs.

306 In conclusion, here we broadened our knowledge of how HC alters the molecular composition of circulating
307 EVs and thoroughly analyzed its effect on CM EVs. According to our results and earlier studies, EVs from
308 both sources display a stressed condition. In addition, these EVs might contribute to the dysregulated cardiac
309 homeostasis and tissue remodeling in HC. Further analysis of these EV-mediated pathophysiological
310 mechanisms may improve our understanding of the interaction between cardiovascular and metabolic
311 diseases.

312 Materials and methods

313 In vivo high cholesterol diet and blood collection

314 All procedures were approved by the National Scientific Ethical Committee on Animal Experimentation
315 and the Semmelweis University's Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee, and all experiments were
316 performed in accordance with the ARRIVE guidelines. Male Wistar rats were fed either with standard (n =
317 11) or high cholesterol (n = 7) chow for 12 weeks. HC chow contained 2% cholesterol and 0.25% cholic
318 acid. Animals were housed in a temperature (22 ± 2 °C)-, and humidity-controlled ($50 \pm 10\%$) room at a 12
319 h light/dark cycle and had free access to laboratory chow and drinking water ad libitum. After the 12-week
320 period, the animals were anesthetized intraperitoneally with 60 mg/kg pentobarbital and their blood was
321 collected from the abdominal aorta into Anticoagulant Citrate Dextrose-A vacuum tubes. Platelet-free
322 plasma (PFP) was obtained by centrifugation twice with $2.500 \times g$ at 4 °C, for 15 min as previously
323 described⁷³. PFP samples were stored at -80 °C until processing (Figure 1 A). No animals were excluded
324 from the study.

325 EV isolation from the plasma

326 Plasma EVs were isolated and purified as previously described by Onódi *et al.*²⁵. In brief, extracellular
327 vesicle isolation was performed by iodixanol (60 w/V% iodixanol in ultrapure water; Axis-Shield, Oslo,
328 Norway) density gradient ultracentrifugation (24 h, $120.000 \times g$, 4 °C). The EV-rich DGUC fractions
329 (Supplementary Figure S1) were loaded into a HiScreen Capto Core 700 column (GE Healthcare Life
330 Sciences) and size exclusion chromatography-based purification was performed. Vezics system
331 (vezics.com) was used to implement the isolation.

332 In vivo metabolomics

333 Metabolomic analysis of 0.01 mL EV- or PFP sample was performed using a Biocrates MxP Quant 500 kit
334 (Biocrates AG, Innsbruck, Austria) according to the manufacturer's instructions, as detailed in the Online
335 Supplementary Material. The analytical procedure was guided by the laboratory information management
336 software Biocrates MetIDQ (version 7.13.11, DB109-Nitrogen-2850 Revision 31995, Base Version 109,
337 Runtime version 1.8.0_181, Runtime architecture amd64; Biocrates A.G., Innsbruck, Austria). Analytical
338 system control and data acquisition were accomplished using Sciex Analyst version 1.5.3. The analytical
339 results were evaluated by MetIDQ and results were analyzed in R⁷⁴. Metabolites were excluded from the
340 analysis if less than half of the measurements (< 7 for CTRL and < 4 for VEH) were below the limit of
341 detection (LOD) in both groups independently for EV and plasma samples. For the analytes included, values
342 below the LOD were imputed with a normal distribution around half of the LOD. For correlation analysis,

343 metabolite types for which at least twelve plasma-EV measurement pairs were available were analyzed with
344 a linear regression model. For both linear regression and statistical analysis, data were log₁₀ transformed.

345 [Culturing and HC treatment of AC16 cells](#)

346 AC16 human cardiomyoblast cells from ATCC were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle medium and
347 Nutrient F12 1:1 mix (DMEM/F12) (Capricorn, Cat. no.: DMEM-12-A) supplemented with 12.5% heat-
348 inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Corning, Cat. no.: 35-079-CV), 2 mM of L-glutamine (Corning, Cat.
349 No.: 25-005.CI), 10 mM of HEPES (N-2-hydroxyethylpiperazine- N-2-ethane sulfonic acid) (Gibco, Cat.
350 No: 15630-056) and 1% Antibiotic-Antimiotic Solution (Corning, Cat. No.: A5955-100ML). Cells were
351 kept at 37 °C in a 5% CO₂/95% air environment and subcultured by trypsinization (TrypLE) (Gibco, Cat.
352 No.: 12604-021) when cells reached 90% of confluence. For HC treatment, cells were kept in medium
353 supplemented with Refeed (Remembrance, Imola, Italy) hypercholesterolemic supplement or its vehicle
354 (0.3% ethanol final concentration) for 48 hours according to Makkos *et al.*⁷⁵ (Figure 2 A). At the end of the
355 treatment, cells were trypsinized and cell count was measured using a hemocytometer and viability was
356 determined by Trypan blue (Cytiva, Cat. No.: SV3008401) staining. Cells were used only if viability reached
357 90%.

358 [Oil Red O staining](#)

359 AC16 cells were seeded on CELLview cell culture microscope slides (Greiner Bio-One, Austria) at a
360 concentration of 20,000 cells / well. After 24 hours, the cells were treated with HC treatment solution, then
361 cultured for another 48 hours at 37 °C in a CO₂ incubator. The cells were fixed in 10% neutrally buffered
362 formalin, washed with ultrapure water and then with 60% isopropanol. The cells were then stained with Oil
363 Red O solution (3 mg/mL) (Sigma, USA, Cat. No.: O0625-25G) for 10 minutes. This was followed by
364 another wash with isopropanol followed by ultrapure water, and the nuclei were labeled with 1:1.000
365 dilution of DAPI (Cell Signaling Technologies, Danvers, MA, USA, Cat. No.: 4083S) for 1 minute, and the
366 samples were covered with Prolong Gold (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) mounting medium and
367 coverslips were applied. Samples were examined with a Leica SP8 confocal microscope. Oil-Red-O dye
368 was excited at 552 nm and the emitted fluorescence was detected in the range of 645-767 nm.

369 [Isolation of EV from AC16 cell culture supernatant](#)

370 A total of 3.5 million AC16 cells were seeded in 175 cm² culture dishes and 24 hours later, the culture
371 medium was changed to FBS-free medium. After 48 hours of incubation, the culturing medium was
372 collected in 50 mL centrifuge tubes and EVs were isolated using differential centrifugation. Cell
373 supernatants were centrifuged at 300×g at 4 °C for 10 min (Hettich Universal 320R; Rotor type: 1494 with
374 Hettich 1427 adaptor). Then supernatants were centrifuged at 2,500×g at 4 °C for 5 min (Hettich Universal

375 320R; Rotor type: 1494 with Hettich 1427 adaptor). The supernatants were transferred into 50 mL centrifuge
376 tubes (Herolab Cat. no.: 253211) and centrifuged at 13,500×g at 4 °C for 40 min (Hermle Z326K; Rotor
377 type: 220.78 V20.). Next, they were transferred into ultracentrifuge tubes (Beckman Coulter, Cat. no.:
378 326823) and centrifuged at 174,900×g at 4 °C for 3 h using an ultracentrifuge (Optima XPN-100; Rotor
379 type: SW32Ti with adaptor 129.7). Pellets were resuspended in 120 µL phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) or
380 120 µL Tris-buffered saline (TBS) for atomic force microscopy (AFM). Protein concentration was measured
381 with light absorbance at 280 nm by Implen N50 (Implen, München, Germany) nanophotometer.

382 Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis

383 EV samples were analyzed by Zeta View PMX 110 (Particle Metrix, Meerbusch, Germany) nanoparticle
384 tracking analysis (NTA) machine calibrated with 100-nm polystyrene beads according to the manufacturer's
385 protocol. Samples were diluted in PBS to a concentration of 50–300 particles in a view of sight. At least 1
386 mL of sample was injected into the machine and automated measurements were performed at 11 positions
387 throughout the measurement cell, with two readouts at each position. Positions for which the software
388 recommended exclusion were excluded from the final evaluation.

389 Instrument parameters were set as: temperature 25 °C, sensitivity 85, frame rate 30 frames per second and
390 shutter speed 100. Post-acquisition parameters were set as: minimum brightness 20, minimum size 5 pixels
391 and maximum size 1000 pixels. Results were multiplied by the dilution factor.

392 For size distribution plot, the mean of all the measurements was calculated, data were smoothed with Loess
393 regression and visualized with ± SEM.

394 Western-blot

395 For Western blotting, EV samples were lysed in radioimmunoprecipitation assay buffer (Cell Signaling
396 Technologies, Danvers, MA, USA) supplemented with 1 mM of PMSF (Roche, Basel, Switzerland), and
397 0.1 mM of sodium fluoride, and complete protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche, Basel, Switzerland). Equal
398 volumes of each sample were mixed with 1/4 volume of Laemmli buffer containing β-mercaptoethanol
399 (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and loaded on Tris-glycine sodium dodecyl sulfate-
400 polyacrylamide gels (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA), and electrophoresed. Proteins were transferred onto a
401 PVDF membrane (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA). Membranes were blocked in 5% bovine serum albumin
402 (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) in Tris-buffered saline containing 0.05% Tween-20 at room temperature for
403 2 h. Primary antibodies used were anti-TSG101 (ab83, Abcam, Cambridge, UK), anti-Alix (sc-53540, Santa
404 Cruz Biotechnology, Dallas, Texas, USA), anti-CD81 (sc-166029, Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Dallas,
405 Texas, USA), anti-albumin (sc-271605, Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Dallas, Texas, USA), Anti-ApoB
406 (MABS2046, (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany), anti-fibrinogen (GTX54019, GeneTex, Irvine, Ca,

407 USA) and anti-HSP70 (sc-66049, Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Dallas, Texas, USA). The presence of
408 individual contaminating organelles was detected using the Organelle Detection Western Blot Cocktail
409 (ab133989, Abcam, Cambridge, UK). The cocktail contained anti-sodium-potassium ATPase (plasma
410 membrane), anti-ATP5A (mitochondria), anti-GAPDH (cytosol) and anti-Histone-H3 (nucleus) antibodies.
411 Anti-mouse IgG, HRP-linked Antibody (7076s, Cell Signaling Technologies, Danvers, MA, USA) and
412 Anti-rabbit IgG, HRP-linked Antibody (7074s, Cell Signaling Technologies, Danvers, MA, USA)
413 secondary antibodies were used to detect the proteins. Signals were visualized using enhanced
414 chemiluminescence kit (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) using Chemidoc XRS+ (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA,
415 USA) and analyzed with Image Lab software (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA).

416 Determination of lipid and phosphatidylcholine content of EVs

417 Lipid content was determined as described previously by Visnovitz *et al.*⁷⁶. In brief, 50 mg of vanillin
418 (Sigma, W310727) was dissolved in 50 mL of 17% phosphoric acid (Sigma, 79617) to create phosphor-
419 vanillin reagent. 200 μ L of 96% sulfuric acid was added either to 40 μ L of 1,2-Dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-
420 phosphocoline (DOPC) (Sigma, P6354) liposome standards, or to 40 μ L of EVs suspended in sterile filtered
421 PBS. After being vortexed, samples and standards were incubated at 90 °C in a fume hood for 20 min. Tubes
422 were cooled down and 120 μ L of phospho-vanillin reagent was added to each tube and 280 μ L of each
423 sample was transferred into a 96-well plate and was incubated at 37 °C for 1 h. Absorbance was determined
424 at 540 nm using a plate reader (Multiskan Go, Thermo Scientific). Total PC content was measured using a
425 colorimetric assay (CS0001, Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany).

426 AFM imaging and force spectroscopy of EVs

427 EV samples were diluted 100-fold with TBS buffer. One hundred μ L of sample was deposited on freshly
428 cleaved mica surface and incubated at 25 \pm 1 °C for 30 minutes. Excess vesicles that did not adsorb on the
429 substrate were removed by gently rinsing with ultrapure water, then 100 μ L of TBS was added. These
430 samples were examined using a Cypher ES atomic force microscope (Asylum Research, Santa Barbara, CA)
431 using Olympus BL AC 40 TS cantilevers (nominal stiffness: 90 pN/nm, resonance frequency: 110 kHz, tip
432 radius: 8 nm; Olympus, Japan) at 25 °C. Prior to measurements, cantilevers were calibrated by the thermal
433 method in air⁷⁷. Then, images were taken in non-contact mode, at 0.5-1 Hz line scanning frequency in buffer,
434 oscillating the cantilever at its resonance frequency. Contact mode measurements were then performed for
435 in situ force spectroscopy on selected spherical vesicles with topographical height exceeding 15 nm. During
436 force spectroscopy, the cantilever was moved at speed of 1 μ m/s from a pre-set height towards the vesicle
437 until a load threshold of 100 pN was reached. It was then immediately retracted at the same speed. Deflection
438 of the cantilever and thus force as a function of cantilever position (force-indentation curve or force curve)
439 were recorded during the process.

440 Image and force curve analysis was implemented using the built-in algorithms of AFM driving software
441 (IgorPro, WaveMetrics Inc., Lake Oswego, OR). Data were collected from a minimum of 5 individual
442 experiments for each treatment group. Image analysis included only the particles with at least 10 nm height.
443 Smaller particles were classified as non-vesicular structures and excluded from the analysis. EV diameter
444 was determined as the diameter of a circle with an area equal to the surface area of the vesicle projected to
445 the substrate. Vesicle height is defined as the difference between the highest point of the vesicle and the
446 substrate. Young modulus of vesicles was obtained by fitting force-vesicle indentation curves from 0
447 (contact point) to 100 pN loading force with the modified Hertz model⁷⁸.

448 Mass spectrometry of EV proteins

449 AC16 EV isolates were vacuum-dried and transferred on dry ice to UCD Conway Institute Mass
450 Spectrometry Resource. Samples were then resuspended in 50 μ L of 50 mM Tris HCl (Thermo Scientific,
451 Waltham, MA, USA), sonicated, and protein concentration was measured using a bicinchoninic acid (BCA)
452 assay kit (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Samples were normalized to protein concentration and
453 dissolved in 6M Urea (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The samples were then reduced by adding
454 8 mM of dithiothreitol (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) and stirred at 30 °C at 1000 rpm for 30 minutes.
455 Samples were then carboxylated by adding 20 mM of iodoacetamide (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany)
456 and stirred at 30 °C at 1000 rpm for 30 minutes. Next, samples were diluted with 50mM of Tris HCL to
457 reduce urea concentration below 2M. Samples were digested by Trypsin (Promega (Corporation, Madison,
458 WI, USA) at 37 °C with 1000 rpm in 1:30 enzyme:sample ratio overnight. Digestion was terminated by
459 adding formic acid (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) to 1% final concentration. Samples were
460 purified on EmporeTM Solid Phase Extraction membranes (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany), eluted in
461 60% acetonitrile and 0.1% Trifluoroacetic acid, vacuum dried and in 0.1% formic acid and each sample was
462 loaded onto an Evosep tip (Evosep Biosystems, Buchwaldsgade, Denmark). The Evosep tips were placed
463 in position on the Evosep One, in a 96-tip box. The autosampler is configured to pick up each tip, elute and
464 separate the peptides using a set chromatography method (30 samples a day)⁷⁹. The mass spectrometer was
465 operated in positive ion mode with a capillary voltage of 1.700 V, dry gas flow of 3 l/min and a dry
466 temperature of 180 °C. All data were acquired with the instrument operating in trapped ion mobility
467 spectrometry (TIMS) mode. Trapped ions were selected for ms/ms using parallel accumulation serial
468 fragmentation (PASEF). A scan range of (100-1700 m/z) was performed at a rate of 5 PASEF MS/MS
469 frames to 1 MS scan with a cycle time of 1.03s⁸⁰. The following chromatography buffers were used: Buffer
470 B: 99.9% acetonitrile, 0.1% formic acid. Buffer A: 99.9% water, 0.1% formic acid. Raw mass spectrometric
471 data have been deposited to the ProteomeXchange Consortium via the PRIDE⁸¹ partner repository with the
472 dataset identifier PXD044594.

473 Analysis of proteomics data

474 The raw data were searched against the Homo sapiens subset of the UniProt Swissprot database (reviewed,
475 12.11.2021) using the search engine Maxquant (release 2.1.4.0)⁸² with specific parameters for trapped ion
476 mobility spectra data dependent acquisition (TIMS DDA). Each peptide used for protein identification met
477 specific Maxquant parameters, i.e., only peptide scores that corresponded to a false discovery rate (FDR) of
478 0.01 were accepted from the Maxquant database search. The normalized protein intensity of each identified
479 protein was used for label-free quantitation (LFQ)⁸³. LFQ intensities were analyzed according to the
480 protocol of Tyanova & Cox³⁷, using R⁷⁴. Proteins that were labelled as *reversed* or *potential contaminants*
481 or *only identified by site* were excluded (see supplementary material). Proteins that were detected in less
482 than half of the samples in all groups were also excluded. Every other protein was defined as identified and
483 processed for quantitative analysis. Data were log₂ transformed and the missing values were imputed with
484 normal distribution around the detection limit. For statistical analysis, log₂ transformed data were used. To
485 calculate fold changes, non-transformed data was used. STRING software^{84,85} was used to visualize protein
486 interaction networks and for gene ontology (GO) enrichment analysis.

487 Monocyte activation assay

488 THP1 human monocytes expressing apoptosis-associated speck-like protein containing a CARD domain
489 fused by green fluorescent protein (ASC-GFP, InvivoGen, Toulouse, France) were maintained in THP1
490 medium consisting of RPMI 1640 medium (Gibco, 21875-034), 10 V/V% heat inactivated FBS (Corning,
491 35-079-CV), 1% L-glutamine (Corning, 30-004-CI), 1% antibiotics-antimycotics (Corning, 25-005-CI), and
492 1% HEPES (Gibco, 15630-080) at a maximum of 6×10^5 cells/mL in a T175 flask. THP1 medium was also
493 supplemented with 100 µg/mL Zeocin (InvivoGen, ant-zn-0.5) for transgene selection at every second
494 passage. Cells were grown at 5% CO₂ 95% air, at 37 °C. All experiments were performed within 10 passages
495 and repeated at least four times.

496 1×10^6 THP1-ASC-GFP cells in 24-well plates were treated with either 100 ng/mL LPS, 10^7 - 10^9 particles/mL
497 HC-EV, CTRL-EV or VEH-EV, corresponding EV supernatants, or whole medium from AC16 cells
498 overnight, and then cells were collected onto ice for flow cytometry analyses.

499 Cells were resuspended in PBS and fixed with 1% PFA at 4 °C for 10 min and washed twice. Flow cytometry
500 was performed using BD FACSCalibur (BD Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA) and evaluated using Flowing
501 software (Turku Bioscience, Turku, Finland). THP1-ASC-GFP cells were gated first on live cells based on
502 SSC and FSC followed by GFP⁺ population analysis. For each measurement, 10,000 events were counted.

503 Quantitative PCR

504 After treatment of THP-1-ASC-GFP cells as described above, cells were lysed in quiazol lysis reagent
505 (Quiagen, Germantown, MD, USA) and stored at -80 °C. Total RNA isolation, cDNA synthesis and qPCR
506 measurements were performed as described earlier⁸⁶. Measurements were performed on a LightCycler 480
507 Real-Time PCR System (Roche Diagnostics, Basel, Switzerland) using LightCycler[®] RNA Master SYBR
508 Green I reagent (Roche Diagnostics, Basel, Switzerland) with primers presented in Supplementary Table
509 S2, with the following protocol: Initiation: 95 °C 2 min; Amplification: (45x) 95 °C 5s, 57 °C 10s, 72 °C
510 20s. Data were analyzed by $\Delta\Delta C_t$ calculation method according to Schmittgen and Livak 2008⁸⁷, using
511 Hypoxanthine Phosphoribosyltransferase 1 (HPRT) as a housekeeping gene.

512 Statistics

513 For statistical analysis and data visualization, the programming language R with ggplot2^{74,88} was used. To
514 create figures, Adobe Illustrator (Adobe, San Jose, CA, USA) was used. For statistical analysis,
515 corresponding parametric statistical probes were applied with a significance level of 0.05. In more detail,
516 multiple t-tests with Benjamini-Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR) adjustment were used for
517 metabolomics data. To analyze AC16 EVs, including NTA, AFM and protein concentration data, and for
518 the analysis of flow cytometry data on THP1-ASC-GFP cells, analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's
519 post-hoc test was applied. ANOVA with FDR adjustment followed by Tukey's post-hoc test was used to
520 analyze proteomics data. For GO enrichment analysis with FDR correction, STRING software was used^{84,85}.
521 Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean.

522

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741 Author contributions

742 CK and SH were the principal investigators of the study. CK, SH, ZG, NVS, CP and PF took part in the
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745 measurements. ZÁ, BK, TB, CC, NK and MK set up the methodology of AFM measurements, coordinated
746 and performed the experiments. NVS, BYW and ALH performed monocyte activation experiments with the
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748 and DM. CK and DK performed formal analysis and data visualization. EB, MK, DM, PF and ZG provided
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750 and approved the final manuscript.

751 Data availability

752 Proteomic mass spectrometry data are available via ProteomeXchange with identifier PXD044594.
753 Processed proteomic and metabolomic data, with the analyzed relative expression data are available as

754 online supplementary material. All other datasets are available from the corresponding author on reasonable
755 request.

756 [Competing interests](#)

757 PF is the founder and CEO, and ZG is the Translational Program Director of Pharmahungary Group, a group
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761 [Ethics approval](#)

762 All procedures were approved by the National Scientific Ethical Committee on Animal Experimentation
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